

A versatile gold leaf immunosensor with a novel functionalization strategy based on Protein L-modified surface for efficient HER2 detection

Ivana Kundacina^{*a}, Silvia Schobesberger^b, Stefan Kittler^c, Helena Thumfart^b, Oliver Spadiut^c, Peter Ertl^b, Nikola Knezevic^a, Vasa Radonic^{*a}

*corresponding authors: ivana.kundacina@biosense.rs; vasarad@biosense.rs;

^a University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute, Dr Zorana Djindjica 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia; ivana.kundacina@biosense.rs; vasarad@biosense.rs; nknezevic@biosense.rs;

^b TU Wien, Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Getreidemarkt 9, 1060 Vienna, Austria silvia.schobesberger@tuwien.ac.at; helena.thumfart@tuwien.ac.at; peter.ertl@tuwien.ac.at;

^c TU Wien, Research Division Integrated Bioprocess Development, Institute of Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering, Gumpendorfer Strasse 1a, 1060 Vienna, Austria; stefan.kittler@tuwien.ac.at; oliver.spadiut@tuwien.ac.at;

Highlights

- Low-cost solution for detection of HER2 cancer biomarker;
- Novel functionalization strategy of gold leaf electrodes with protein L;
- High sensitivity of HER2 detection without signal enrichment;
- Limit of detection 0.02 ng mL⁻¹ in buffer and 0.03 ng mL⁻¹ in cell culture medium;
- Platform easily adaptable for detection of antibodies and fragments;

Abstract

Although various sensors specifically developed for target analytes are available, affordable biosensing solutions with broad applicability are limited. In this study, a cost-effective biosensor for detecting human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) was developed using custom-made gold leaf electrodes (GLEs). A novel strategy for antibody immobilization on a gold surface, mediated by protein L, was examined using commercial screen-printed gold electrodes and GLEs. This versatile immobilization strategy enables the application of the functionalized GLEs for the detection of antibodies and antigens. A self-assembled monolayer of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA) on the gold surface, was used to immobilize protein L, further binding trastuzumab to detect HER2 using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The HER2 detection was examined in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and supplemented cell culture medium. The modified GLEs showed good specificity and high sensitivity of HER2 detection without any enrichment steps, achieving a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.02 ng mL⁻¹ in PBS and 0.03 ng mL⁻¹ in cell culture medium, making the proposed immunosensor a cost-effective and sensitive solution for detection in complex biological matrices.

Keywords: gold leaf electrodes, screen-printed electrodes, electrochemical immunosensor, protein L, trastuzumab, HER2

1. Introduction

Breast cancer is one of the most commonly diagnosed types of cancer in women worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 2.3 million women were diagnosed with breast cancer in 2020, resulting in 685,000 deaths [1], while the survival rate for metastatic cancer is only 20% at 5 years [2]. For that reason, timely detection of specific cancer biomarkers, such as HER2, is crucial in battling this disease. HER2 is a protein receptor that plays a key role in the regulation of cell growth and division. In healthy individuals, the presence of HER2 is essential for maintaining healthy tissue, but mutations that lead to overexpression of HER2 are associated with aggressive forms of breast

cancer. In the blood of healthy people, the concentration of HER2 is in the range of 4 – 14 ng mL⁻¹, while in HER2-positive breast cancer patients, the level increases to 15 – 75 ng mL⁻¹ [3,4]. In general, HER2-positive patients have a more aggressive form of the disease and a worse prognosis than HER2-negative patients. However, in 1998 and 2000 in the USA and European Union, respectively, Herceptin (trastuzumab) was approved for medical applications for the treatment of HER2-positive breast cancer patients [5]. This monoclonal antibody is specifically designed to target and block HER2 on the surface of cancer cells from receiving growth signals. Therefore, the early detection of this biomarker enables the treatment start in an early phase and enhances the likelihood to battle the cancer.

Standard methods for breast cancer diagnostics include techniques based on imaging like ultrasound, magnetic resonance, and molecular breast imaging; gene expression techniques such as radioimmunoassay, immunohistochemistry, and enzyme immunoassay; and invasive methods such as biopsy [6]. However, novel solutions for cancer biomarker detection are based on the development of biosensors and their integration into point-of-care devices for routine blood testing. Besides the detection of HER2 for early diagnosis, the establishment of in vitro disease models, particularly through organ-on-a-chip technology, is prevalent for studying drug candidates, with an increasing emphasis on combining this technology with biosensors for close monitoring of microphysiological systems [2,7–9].

Different optical [10,11], field effect transistor-based [12,13], colorimetric [14–16], mass-change [17,18], and electrochemical biosensors [19–21] have been proposed for early-stage diagnostics of breast cancer [22]. Among the proposed solutions, electrochemical biosensors have shown the potential to achieve the best sensitivity by introducing nanomaterials [23], examining different immobilization protocols of biorecognition elements [24–26], and signal amplification strategies [27]. However, the massive production of electrodes and stability of the immobilized biorecognition layers is costly and difficult challenge. Conventional technologies for electrode fabrication such as physical and chemical vapor deposition techniques require capital equipment, a cleanroom facility, and the produced thin films can be damaged easily. Other technologies such as inkjet printing and screen printing are suitable for the massive production of electrodes with limited substrate choice since the printed layer requires a sintering process. In addition, the reproducibility of electrodes on the micron level depends on screen imperfections, and impurities and organic components of the ink can interfere with the biosensing layers [28,29]. Therefore, a novel, low-cost technology for gold electrode fabrication was proposed in our recent work [30]. The proposed technology uses laminated layers of low-cost gold leaves and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) sheets, treated with laser ablation to realize the designed electrode geometry. This technology enables the realization of multiple electrodes in a single batch, and the rough surface properties enable the sensitive detection of bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella Typhimurium* without any enrichment steps [30,31].

In addition to the gold surface and structural quality, the sensing layer architecture of immobilized biorecognition elements is an important step in biosensor development. Protein L is a versatile binding ligand with unique capabilities for the detection and purification of antibodies and antibody fragments. Unlike other affinity ligands such as protein A or G, protein L interacts with immunoglobulin light chains. Despite the potential of protein L as a binding ligand in previous studies [32], no electrochemical biosensor incorporation of this ligand has been employed so far. Protein L exhibits remarkable specificity for the detection of antibody fragments and monoclonal antibodies, especially IgGs derived from humans, [32–34], making it a good candidate for antibody immobilization for a versatile biosensing platform. Although a limited number of strategies for antibody purification based on protein L immobilization have been proposed [35,36] its potential in electrochemical biosensors remains unexplored.

For such purpose, we set forth to develop a GLE-based electrochemical biosensor for the detection of the cancer biomarker HER2 mediated by protein L and trastuzumab. The produced GLEs were

characterized in terms of composition, electroactive surface and responsiveness to different concentrations of redox probes prepared in deionized water (DIW), potassium chloride and PBS. In addition, the antibody immobilization was examined and characterized via a immunoassay, Raman spectroscopy, and EIS. The detection sensitivity was electrochemically tested using commercial gold screen-printed electrodes and GLEs. Finally, the application potential of the GLE-based biosensor was validated for the detection of HER2 in cell medium.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials and fabrication of gold leaf electrodes

As it was described in our previous work [30], two layers of gold leaves (Pozlata Dimitrijevic, Serbia) were laminated at 180 °C (Laminator PDA3 330C, PINGDA, China) on the surface of 0.5 mm thick multilayered structure of PVC sheets (Fellowes Brands, Poland) covered with polytetrafluoroethylene – PTFE spray (Wurth, Serbia). The laser ablation of a gold leaf sheet was performed using a Nd:YAG laser (Power Line D-100, Rofin-Sinar, Germany) in order to realize the electrode geometry.

2.2. Chemicals

Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), Dulbecco's PBS (modified without CaCl₂ and MgCl₂), 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA), N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), bovine serum albumin (BSA), Tween® 20, potassium chloride (KCl), sodium carbonate anhydrous (Na₂CO₃), sodium bicarbonate anhydrous (NaHCO₃), potassium ferricyanide (K₃[Fe(CN)₆]), and potassium ferrocyanide (K₄[Fe(CN)₆]) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA), while 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC-HCl), Peptipure ≥99% were procured from ROTH and absolute ethanol from Chem-Lab NV (Belgium). Human HER2 were purchased from ACRO Biosystems (USA), antibody for *E. coli* (ab137967) from Abcam (USA), and Fibrinogen (FBG) from CSL Behring (USA). Fluorescent probe AlexaFluor 488, anti-human IgG (H+L) (Invitrogen) and Cell culture medium (Gibco CO₂ Independent Medium) were purchased from ThermoFisher Scientific. Cell culture medium supplemented with 10% serum (Fetal Bovine Serum, Sigma-Aldrich), 1% antibiotics (Penicillin-Streptomycin, Sigma-Aldrich), and 1% L-glutamine. Protein L was recombinantly produced in *E. coli* and characterized as described in [34].

2.3. Equipment

Electrochemical measurements were performed using the Multichannel Potentiostat (Biologic VMP-3e, France) connected to a PC with EC-lab software. Fluorescence measurements were done using a Multimode plate reader (EnSpire® 2300, Perkin Elmer), Raman spectroscopy using XploRA Plus Raman Spectrometer (Horiba, France) and bio-layer interferometry using a Octet RED96e (PALL FortéBio, CA, USA) device. A connection of electrodes (custom-made GLEs and commercial screen-printed electrodes, Dropsens 220AT, Metrohm) with the potentiostat were realized using a holder (Original 1 PCS 2.54mm Single Row 3P PCB Clip Clamp Fixture Probe Pogo Pin, China).

2.4. Bio-Layer Interferometry

The functionality of protein L was verified with bio-layer interferometry. Namely, different concentrations of protein L (25, 50, 75, 100, 200 and 400 nM, respectively) were incubated with trastuzumab and their binding with trastuzumab was examined.

2.5. Functionalization steps

For the functionalization of the of the biosensor, 1 mM MUA prepared in absolute ethanol was incubated at the working electrode (WE) at 4 °C. The droplet with a volume of 1 μL is drop casted on the WE, and the incubation was done in the dark. After 16 h of incubation, rinsing of the electrode surface was done initially with absolute ethanol, and then with DIW. Activation of carboxyl groups of MUA was performed by applying 10 μL of 50 mM NHS/50 mM EDC prepared in PBS, to the WE by

one-hour incubation in the dark. The electrode was then rinsed with DIW. Activated carboxyl groups have an affinity for binding amino groups of proteins, so in the next step of functionalization, 10 μL of protein L with 0.1 mg mL^{-1} concentration was incubated for 1 h. After incubation and rinsing protein L, a BSA concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ was applied and incubated for 20 min in the dark in order to prevent a non-specific binding nor non-specific contribution to the signal. Subsequently, trastuzumab with concentrations in the range of 0.1 ng mL^{-1} to 1000 ng mL^{-1} was incubated for 20 min, rinsed with DIW, and characterized with the redox probe in EIS measurements. After exposing the electrode to increasing concentration of trastuzumab, the electrode was exposed to increasing concentrations of HER2 in the range of 0.1 ng mL^{-1} to 1000 ng mL^{-1} . The incubation of 20 min, rinsing with DIW, and EIS characterization were repeated for each concentration of HER2.

2.6. Electrochemical characterization of gold leaf electrodes

The CV characterization of bare GLE in 0.5 M sulphuric acid was obtained in the potential range from 0 V to 1.55 V vs. gold RE and scan rate 0.5 V s^{-1} , while stability tests were performed with the redox probe in the potential range from -0.4 V to 0.4 V vs. gold RE. The scan rate was 0.5 V s^{-1} and a voltammogram was made in 100 cycles. In addition, the electroactive surface was determined from the series of experiments with the redox probe in the same potential range, for cycles made with scan rates in the range of 0.1 V s^{-1} – 1 V s^{-1} with steps of 0.1 V s^{-1} . The linear dependence of the square root of the scan rate and oxidation and reduction peaks were used to calculate the electroactive surface of the electrodes from the slope using the Randles-Sevcik equation [37] given by equation (1):

$$A = \frac{k}{2.69 \cdot 10^5 \cdot C \cdot D^{1/2} \cdot n^{3/2}} \quad (1)$$

where k represents the slope coefficient of the linear dependence, $2.69 \cdot 10^5 \text{ C mol}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1/2}$ constant, C concentration of ions, n the number of electrons participating in the half-reaction, and D the diffusion coefficient ($6.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) [38].

The biosensor detection of HER2 was based on the EIS principle. EIS measurements were done in the frequency range of 1 Hz to 100 kHz, with a direct potential set to zero and a potential amplitude of 10 mV. All measurements were performed versus an open circuit potential in a two-electrode system, where counter and reference electrodes were connected to the same potential.

2.7. Fluorescent assay

The fluorescent assay was done in a 96-well plate, and measurements were performed with a plate reader spectrophotometer. Initially, the wells were coated with 0.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ protein L or 0.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ HER2 and incubated overnight at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Then the plate was washed 4 times with 200 μL of washing buffer (PBS + 0.05% Tween20). Afterward, 100 μL of trastuzumab was added and incubated for 2 h at room temperature. The washing procedure was repeated 4 times with 200 μL of washing buffer and subsequently, a secondary antibody with a fluorescent probe was added in the next step. Briefly, 100 μL of 1:1000 diluted fluorescent goat anti-human IgG was added to the plate wells and incubated for 1 h at room temperature. Afterward, the plate was rinsed 6 times with 200 μL of washing buffer and fluorescence was measured.

2.8. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectra were measured with a laser using a wavelength of 532 nm, in a wavenumber range from 100 to 2000 cm^{-1} , power of 9 mW, and 10 recordings with time exposures of 20 s. A glass slide with 50 nm gold layer was used as a substrate.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrode design

Fig. 1a presents a planar three-electrode system design, where the WE, counter (CE), and reference electrodes (RE) were realized in gold leaves. The overall dimension of the platform is 10.7×28.7 mm, with a pin distance of 2.54 mm which corresponds to standard electronic connecting components. In order to compare the responses of GLEs with commercial screen-printed electrodes, the WE radius is set to 2 mm, which is the same as the radius of commercial electrodes.

3.2. Biosensor construction

A schematic view of the functionalization layers is presented in Fig. 1b. A self-assembled monolayer of MUA is formed by the binding of thiol groups to the gold surface. The carboxyl group on the opposite end provides MUA with the possibility of binding protein L, by activating the carboxyl groups using NHS/EDC chemistry. The affinity of protein L for binding IgG antibodies enables trastuzumab immobilization and subsequently detection of HER2 cancer biomarker. To prevent non-specific binding, BSA is introduced as a blocking step in the functionalization process. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1c, where the GLE is placed in the electrode holder with 60 μ L droplet volume.

Fig. 1. (a) Dimensions of the GLE in mm, R = radius; (b) Biosensor functionalization; (c) Experimental setup.

3.3. Electrochemical characterization of GLEs

The described GLEs were characterized in terms of composition, effective surface area and signal stability through CV experiments. In addition, the response of EIS was used to examine the sensitivity for different concentrations of potassium ferro/ferricyanide redox probe prepared in DIW, potassium chloride, and PBS.

Cyclic voltammetry in sulfuric acid was performed on GLE to determine the composition of the electrode surface. CV measurements resulted in a voltammogram (Fig. 2a) that contains characteristic oxidation and reduction peaks of gold, at 0.85 V and 0.52 V vs. gold RE, respectively. In addition, the voltammogram for GLE showed narrow and sharp peaks, indicating a fast electrochemical reaction and no charge accumulation. In addition, the stability experiments resulted in a stable signal with sharp peaks of iron oxidation and reduction within the redox couple (Fig. 2b).

In order to study the effective surface area of the GLE and the commercially-available Dropsens electrode, a series of experiments has been performed with 10 mM potassium ferro/ferricyanide in PBS. The inset of Fig. 2c presents voltammograms obtained using GLE with different scan rates. Fig. 2c presents the oxidation and reduction current peaks of the iron redox couple versus the square root of the scan rate where a linear increase can be determined. With increasing scan rate the potential change occurs more rapidly in time, i.e., more energy is transferred to the ions in solution, resulting in a higher current. Similar results were obtained for the Dropsens electrodes, shown in Fig. A.1.

In addition to the electroactive surface, the roughness factor was calculated as the ratio between the geometric and electroactive surfaces of the electrode. Namely, considering that Dropsens and GLE have the same geometric area of the WE equal to 0.12 cm^2 , the roughness factor describes the extent of electrode surface participation in the reaction, i.e., contribution to the signal. For GLE the roughness factor was calculated to be 1.3, whereas for the Dropsens electrode, it was 0.58, which indicates that the Dropsens electrode contains other components. This is most likely caused by the organic components in the paste used in screen printing, which do not participate in the reaction on the surface. However, in the case of GLE, this factor is greater than one, which confirms their roughness and large specific surface area. The rough surface properties of GLE were confirmed in our previous study via 3D profile [30]. The results show that the GLE has a larger electroactive surface compared to Dropsens.

In order to test the sensitivity of the GLE, concentrations of 0.5, 1, 5, and 10 mM potassium ferrocyanide/ferricyanide were prepared in 10 mM potassium chloride, 10 mM PBS, and DIW, and EIS was performed (Fig. A.2). The measured impedance decreased with increasing concentration of the redox couple. As shown in Figs. 2d and 2e, the Nyquist plots of the redox couple prepared in DIW and 10 mM potassium chloride indicate different solution resistance values since each redox sample concentration has a different real part of the impedance. For the redox couple prepared in 10 mM PBS buffer, the real part of the impedance has similar values for different concentrations. This consistency can be attributed to the properties of PBS, which effectively buffers pH changes.

Fig. 2. Characterization of GLEs; (a) CV of gold in sulphuric acid; (b) Stability of signal in redox probe over 100 scans; (c) Oxidation and reduction peaks in the function of square root of scan rate; inset: Voltammograms of redox probe for scan rates in the range $0.1 - 1 \text{ V s}^{-1}$; (d) Nyquist plots for redox probe prepared in DIW; inset: 5 mM and 10 mM redox probe; (e) Nyquist plots for redox probe prepared in potassium chloride; inset: 5 mM and 10 mM redox probe; (f) Nyquist plots for redox probe prepared in PBS; inset: 5 mM and 10 mM redox probe.

3.4. Fluorescence immunoassay and Bio-Layer Interferometry

As previously mentioned, a fluorescence immunoassay was used to confirm the binding of protein L and trastuzumab, as well as trastuzumab and HER2 in the range of $0.015 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ to $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, as shown in Figs. 3a and b. Both results show binding events, i.e., the signal increases with higher trastuzumab concentrations. A S-curve was used for data fitting, showing a linear trend in the concentration range $0.03 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ to $0.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, after which a saturation can be observed both for protein L and HER2. Besides, bio-layer interferometry additionally confirmed the binding of protein L with trastuzumab (Fig. A.3).

3.5. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was used to characterize the functionalization steps of the biosensor. The existence of newly formed layers is determined for each functionalization step on the gold surface, after applying MUA and after binding of protein L. As it was mentioned, the linker MUA forms a self-assembled monolayer on the gold through thiol group. Earlier studies show that the thiol (-SH) group binds to gold by chemisorption [39,40]. A peak, originating from the Au-S bond was detected in the spectrum at 250 cm^{-1} , which is in agreement with the previously published results [41–43](Fig. 3c). To analyse the Raman spectrum after applying protein L, deconvolution of the peaks in the range of $1200\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was performed and compared (Figs. 3d and e) in order to detect amine groups of protein L. With Raman spectroscopy, several vibrational modes can be used to detect and analyze the protein structure. The following three peaks are of primary interest for the identification of different confirmations of the protein structure: amide I (stretching vibration of C=O range $1600\text{--}1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$), amide II ($1480\text{--}1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$), and amide III (both associated with the coupling by that C–N stretching and N–H bending vibrations of the peptide group $1230\text{--}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) [44]. The results presented in Fig. 3e show the occurrence of two characteristic peaks at 1556 cm^{-1} and at 1756 cm^{-1} after the application of protein L, which corresponds to amide II and amide I bond peaks, respectively.

3.6. Electrochemical characterization of functionalization steps

The binding of trastuzumab to protein L and HER2 was confirmed in an immunoassay with fluorescent readout and bio-layer interferometry. After that, electrochemical characterization using EIS was used to study the binding of each functionalization layer to the WE. Fig. 3f presents Nyquist plots after each functionalization step for GLE, while for the Dropsens electrode the plot is shown in Fig. A.4. To achieve a complete semicircle with a diffusion tail, a concentration of 1 mM MUA was used for GLEs, while a concentration of 10 mM was used for Dropsens electrodes. After applying the self-assembled MUA layer, protein L and then BSA were applied. In both cases, Dropsens and GLE electrodes exhibited an increase in impedance, indicating the formation of a functionalization layer on the surface.

Fig. 3. (a) Fluorescence immunoassay, binding of trastuzumab with protein L; Error bars present standard deviation of three samples; (b) Fluorescence immunoassay, binding of trastuzumab with HER2; Error bars present standard deviation of three samples; (c) Raman spectroscopy in the range 100

– 2000 cm^{-1} ; (d) Raman spectroscopy after MUA deposition in the range 1200 – 1800 cm^{-1} with deconvoluted peaks; (e) Raman spectroscopy after protein L deposition in the range 1200 – 1800 cm^{-1} with deconvoluted peaks; (f) Electrochemical characterization of each functionalization step on GLE.

3.7. Detection of HER2 with Dropsens and GLEs

To further characterize the functionalized surface, increasing concentrations of trastuzumab in the range of 0.1 ng mL^{-1} to 1000 ng mL^{-1} were incubated, as shown in Fig. 4 (for Dropsens electrode Fig. A.5). With higher trastuzumab concentration, the number of antibodies bound to protein L on the electrode surface increases, which is reflected in the rise of impedance. After repeated incubations of trastuzumab, the biosensor was exposed to increasing concentrations of the cancer biomarker HER2 in the range of 0.1 ng mL^{-1} to 1000 ng mL^{-1} . The results in Fig. 4b show an increase of impedance with elevated HER2 concentration. Finally, the results were fitted with a standard Randles circuit [45] (where R_{sol} presents solution resistance, R_{ct} charge transfer resistance, W Warburg element, and CPE constant phase element) presented in insets of Figs. 4c and d. The relative signal change was calculated in relation to the BSA-functionalized electrode for results of trastuzumab detection, while for HER2 detection, it was in relation to 1000 ng mL^{-1} trastuzumab. For GLEs, the results in Fig. 4c show an increase with the elevating concentration of trastuzumab. In the case of the Dropsens electrode, as shown in Fig. 4c, saturation occurred after 100 ng mL^{-1} . The detection response of trastuzumab for GLE is described by a linear equation $y = 39.978x + 62.195$, $R^2 = 0.9854$, (Dropsens electrode: $y = 14.118x + 17.774$, $R^2 = 0.9763$). Both electrodes demonstrated a good linearity in detecting trastuzumab using the proposed configuration. For the detection of the cancer biomarker, as shown in Fig. 4d, the GLE exhibited a linear growing trend, $y = 12.145x + 24.589$, $R^2 = 0.9507$, while the Dropsens HER2 detection curve showed a typical sigmoid shape with saturation after 10 ng mL^{-1} , which is a lower concentration than in case of HER2 positive cancer patients.

Fig. 4. (a) Nyquist plots for different concentrations of trastuzumab; (b) Nyquist plots for different concentrations of HER2; (c) Comparison of the relative change of the signal versus BSA saturated

electrode for different concentrations of trastuzumab – GLE and Dropsens responses; Results are presented as mean value of three measurements with standard deviation. (d) Comparison of the relative change of the signal versus trastuzumab saturated electrode for different concentrations of HER2 – GLE and Dropsens responses. Results are presented as mean value of three measurements with standard deviation. The presented results demonstrate significantly better performance in sensor detection realized using GLEs compared to Dropsens electrodes.

3.8. Specificity tests

To test the specificity of the developed biosensor, the detection was examined with non-specific proteins prepared in PBS. Fig. 5a presents the compared detection responses for various concentrations of the specific biomarker HER2 and non-specific proteins such as *E. coli* antibody, BSA, and fibrinogen (FBG) prepared in PBS, tested at a concentration of 100 ng mL⁻¹. The presented results show that the signals of the specific biomarker for concentrations >1 ng mL⁻¹ are significantly higher compared to non-specific ones. In real samples, large concentrations of non-specific proteins are rarely found, so this result does not diminish the detection potential of the proposed sensor.

3.9. Detection in cell medium

Finally, the robustness of the biosensor and the detection method was tested in cell culture medium (10% serum, 1% antibiotics, 1% L-glutamine, and 88% medium). HER2 in the range of 0.1 ng mL⁻¹ to 1000 ng mL⁻¹ was measured in 10-fold diluted cell culture medium. Considering that the medium is a complex matrix with numerous non-specific components that may contribute to the signal and lead to higher impedance, a control involving surface saturation of the electrode by incubating the medium without the specific biomarker was conducted. Initially, the sensor saturation was performed during a 2-hour incubation of the medium without the cancer biomarker. Subsequently, a repeated incubation of the medium for 20 minutes was done to confirm the signal's constancy without the cancer biomarker. This step aimed to determine whether the signal contribution originated from the specific biomarker rather than non-specific components of the medium, which might adhere to the surface due to electrostatic or other interactions. The results in Fig. 5b show a consistent signal after the repeated incubation of the medium, confirming that the electrode is saturated with non-specific components from the medium. This indicates that the contribution to the increase in impedance in samples with HER2 does not originate from the medium.

Final validation for the detection of the cancer biomarker in the medium was conducted by incubating the electrode for 20 minutes with increasing concentrations of the cancer biomarker in cell culture medium, using a GLE previously saturated with the medium. The graph in Fig. 5c shows sensor response results with Nyquist plots without a diffusion tail. For this reason, the proposed electrical circuit for fitting the results, presented in the inset graph, does not include a Warburg element. Additionally, the results show that the impedance increases linearly with higher HER2 concentrations. The curve representing the dependence of the relative change in charge transfer resistance is shown in Fig. 5d, showing a linear relationship described by the equation $y = 16.62x + 29.765$, $R^2 = 0.9431$. These presented results demonstrate the excellent detection potential of the proposed sensor, even in complex matrices such as cell culture medium.

Fig. 5. (a) Specificity tests for GLE-based HER2 immunosensor (AB = antibody, FBG = fibrinogen); Results are presented as mean value with standard deviation ($n=3$). (b) Control test: Repeated cell medium incubation after surface saturation; Results are presented as mean value with standard deviation ($n=3$). (c) Nyquist plots with equivalent Randles circuit used for fitting the data of HER2 detection in cell medium; (d) Relative change of the signal versus medium saturated surface for different concentrations in the cell medium. Error bars in the graph present standard deviations of three measurements.

4. Discussion

In this study, protein L was used for the immobilization of antibodies on the electrode surface for application in electrochemical biosensing for the first time. In contrast, proteins A and G, well known immunoglobulin binding proteins, were already proposed in the literature for the immobilization and functionalization of biosensors [33]. These proteins are commonly used in antibody purification, either covalently attached to agarose or as bioconjugated nanoparticles [33,46]. Protein L possesses a distinctive advantage attributable to its specific interaction with light chains, facilitating the binding to a broader range of immunoglobulins, including antibody fragments as well [32]. Consequently, we believe the proposed strategy of immobilizing antibodies and fragments through protein L is a promising strategy to establish a universal platform, circumventing the necessity for the individual development of biosensors at the initial stage of immobilization.

The potential of the proposed immunosensor was validated by detecting the HER2 biomarker in PBS and in diluted supplemented cell culture medium. The LOD was calculated based on the average measured signal for blank and the standard deviation of measurements [47], specifically, by adding three times standard deviation to the mean value of the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) signal. Detection limits were determined to be 0.02 ng mL^{-1} in PBS, and 0.03 ng mL^{-1} in cell culture medium. The

immunosensor showed higher LOD in the complex matrix since the sensing surface was saturated with non-specific components of the cell culturing medium and probably blocked the specific binding places on the biosensor surface. Nevertheless, these values are significantly lower than the concentrations of HER2 detectable in healthy individuals and HER2-positive patients, making the proposed immunosensor a good candidate for cancer biomarker sensing. Beside sensing HER2, we demonstrated the potential of the proposed immunosensor to detect an antibody (trastuzumab). This highlights the broad adaptability of the proposed setup for potential applications in medicine and the pharmaceutical industry.

Table 1 compares the GLE-based HER2 biosensor with other electrochemical biosensors proposed in the literature. In general, commonly used substrates for electrochemical detection are gold [48] and carbon electrodes [49]. To increase the effective surface area, amplify the signal and immobilize biorecognition elements for the sensor surface, nanomaterials of different dimensionalities were used: nanoparticles such as gold [50–52], rhodium [4], and iron [51], 2D nanomaterials like antimonene (AMNFs) [53], graphene and graphene oxide [4] and 1D nanomaterials like carbon nanotubes [54]. Recent studies incorporated metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) for biosensor implementation with exceptionally sensitive detection properties [52,53] with LODs in femtograms per millilitre. Other studies use conductive polymers and hydrogels [49,50] for the detection of biomarkers. Each of the proposed biosensors, with its LOD and dynamic detection range, meets the requirements for the sensitivity and specificity of HER2 cancer biomarker detection. However, the proposed technologies require a facility for nanotechnology, expensive equipment, chemicals, and trained personnel for the realization of each described sensor. Furthermore, the proposed method based on GLEs exceeds all other solutions in terms of simplicity and price of substrate fabrication. Multiple electrodes can be produced from a single batch, reducing the estimated cost of each electrode to one-tenth of that of commercial screen-printed electrodes. Additionally, the production of protein L was optimized previously, reducing the price of this affinity ligand significantly [34].

Table 1. Comparison of the proposed sensor with other biosensors from the literature. (¹3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane, ²horseradish peroxidase, ³poly (3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): polystyrene sulfonate, ⁴differential pulse voltammetry, ⁵square wave voltammetry)

Detection method	Material	Biorecognition element	Dynamic range (ng mL ⁻¹)	LOD (ng mL ⁻¹)	Ref.
DPV ⁴	Graphene-decorated rhodium nanoparticles	Aptamer	10 – 500	0.667	[4]
DPV	GCE with PEDOT and peptide hydrogel	Antibody	0.1 – 1000	45 × 10 ⁻³	[49]
DPV	GCE with PEG and AuNPs	Peptide	0.001 - 1000	4.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	[50]
DPV	GCE with antiHER2/APTMS ¹ -Fe ₃ O ₄	Antibody	5 × 10 ⁻⁴ - 50	2 × 10 ⁻⁵	[51]
DPV	SP gold electrode	Antibody	0.5 - 25	0.59	[48]
DPV	AuNPs@HRP ² @ZIF-8	Peptide	50 × 10 ⁻⁶ - 50	16.8 × 10 ⁻⁶	[52]
SQV ⁵	Cd ²⁺ -aptamer@AMNFs@ZIF-67 nanocomposite	Aptamer	0 - 1000	4.8 × 10 ⁻⁶	[53]
SQV	GCE with PEDOT:PSS ³ and AuNPs	Aptamers	0.01- 1000	1.979 × 10 ⁻⁶	[54]
EIS	Gold leaf electrodes	Antibody	0.1 – 1000	0.02	This work

5. Conclusions

In this study a cost-effective immunosensor for the detection of trastuzumab and the cancer biomarker HER2 using custom-made GLEs was presented. The biosensor employed a novel strategy of antibody immobilization on a gold surface mediated by protein L. Electrochemical characterization using CV and EIS demonstrated the bigger roughness factor, i.e. electroactive surface of the GLE in comparison with commercial screen-printed electrodes, and consequently better biosensing performance. The modified GLEs exhibited a high specificity and sensitivity for HER2 detection without requiring enrichment steps. The proposed immunosensor achieved LOD of 0.02 ng mL⁻¹ in PBS and 0.03 ng mL⁻¹ in cell culture medium, which meets the requirements for the detection of HER2. In addition, the biosensing principle employing protein L as an immobilization element demonstrates the possibility of adapting the biosensor depending on the application.

Credit author statement

Ivana Kundacina: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft; **Silvia Schobesberger:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing; **Stefan Kittler:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing; **Helena Thumfart:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing; **Oliver Spadiut:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision; **Peter Ertl:** Writing - review & editing, Resources, Project administration; **Nikola Knezevic:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding Acquisition; **Vasa Radonic:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the Europe Commission's Horizon 2020 Twinning program NANOFACTS (GA No. 952259) and Europe Commission's Horizon 2020 Teaming program ANTARES (GA No. 664387). IK, VR, and NK acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovations of the Republic of Serbia (GA No. 451-03-47/2023-01/200358). IK acknowledges Sara Joksovic for support on Raman measurements.

References

- [1] World Health Organisation, Breast cancer statistics, (2023). <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/breast-cancer> (accessed December 1, 2023).
- [2] P. Boix-Montesinos, P.M. Soriano-Teruel, A. Armiñán, M. Orzáez, M.J. Vicent, The past, present, and future of breast cancer models for nanomedicine development., *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 173 (2021) 306–330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2021.03.018>.
- [3] S.K. Arya, P. Zhuravski, P. Jolly, M.R. Batistuti, M. Mulato, P. Estrela, Capacitive aptasensor based on interdigitated electrode for breast cancer detection in undiluted human serum., *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 102 (2018) 106–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2017.11.013>.
- [4] M. Sadeghi, S. Kashanian, S.M. Naghib, E. Arkan, A high-performance electrochemical aptasensor based on graphene-decorated rhodium nanoparticles to detect HER2-ECD oncomarker in liquid biopsy., *Sci. Rep.* 12 (2022) 3299. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-07230-3>.

- [5] A. Lebeau, [Herceptin therapy in breast cancer: new indication?], *Verh Dtsch Ges Pathol.* 90 (2006) 99–106.
- [6] S. Chupradit, S.A. Jasim, D. Bokov, M.Z. Mahmoud, A.B. Roomi, K. Hachem, M. Rudiansyah, W. Suksatan, R. Bidares, Recent advances in biosensor devices for HER-2 cancer biomarker detection., *Anal. Methods.* 14 (2022) 1301–1310. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ay00111j>.
- [7] S. Fuchs, S. Johansson, A.Ø. Tjell, G. Werr, T. Mayr, M. Tenje, In-Line Analysis of Organ-on-Chip Systems with Sensors: Integration, Fabrication, Challenges, and Potential., *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* 7 (2021) 2926–2948. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbiomaterials.0c01110>.
- [8] L. Mou, K. Mandal, M.M. Mecwan, A.L. Hernandez, S. Maity, S. Sharma, R.D. Herculano, S. Kawakita, V. Jucaud, M.R. Dokmeci, A. Khademhosseini, Integrated biosensors for monitoring microphysiological systems., *Lab Chip.* 22 (2022) 3801–3816. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2lc00262k>.
- [9] B. Subia, U.R. Dahiya, S. Mishra, J. Ayache, G.V. Casquillas, D. Caballero, R.L. Reis, S.C. Kundu, Breast tumor-on-chip models: From disease modeling to personalized drug screening., *J. Control. Release.* 331 (2021) 103–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2020.12.057>.
- [10] S. Akgönüllü, A. Denizli, Recent advances in optical biosensing approaches for biomarkers detection, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics: X.* 12 (2022) 100269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosx.2022.100269>.
- [11] K. Nejadi-Koshki, F. Fathi, A. Arabzadeh, A. Mohammadzadeh, Biomarkers and optical based biosensors in cardiac disease detection: early and accurate diagnosis., *Anal. Methods.* 15 (2023) 5441–5458. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3ay01414b>.
- [12] R. Hao, L. Liu, J. Yuan, L. Wu, S. Lei, Recent advances in field effect transistor biosensors: designing strategies and applications for sensitive assay., *Biosensors (Basel).* 13 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios13040426>.
- [13] L. Li, X. Liu, T. Wei, K. Wang, Z. Zhao, J. Cao, Y. Liu, Z. Zhang, Carbon Nanotube Field-Effect Transistor Biosensor with an Enlarged Gate Area for Ultra-Sensitive Detection of a Lung Cancer Biomarker., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* 15 (2023) 27299–27306. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.3c02700>.
- [14] Y.J. Chi, B. Ryu, S. Ahn, W.-G. Koh, A colorimetric biosensor based on a biodegradable fluidic device capable of efficient saliva sampling and salivary biomarker detection, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical.* 396 (2023) 134601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2023.134601>.
- [15] M.R. Hasan, P. Sharma, R. Pilloton, M. Khanuja, J. Narang, Colorimetric biosensor for the naked-eye detection of ovarian cancer biomarker PDGF using citrate modified gold nanoparticles, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics: X.* 11 (2022) 100142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosx.2022.100142>.
- [16] L. Xiao, A. Zhu, Q. Xu, Y. Chen, J. Xu, J. Weng, Colorimetric Biosensor for Detection of Cancer Biomarker by Au Nanoparticle-Decorated Bi₂Se₃ Nanosheets., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* 9 (2017) 6931–6940. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.6b15750>.
- [17] C. Lino, S. Barrias, R. Chaves, F. Adegas, J.R. Fernandes, P. Martins-Lopes, Development of a QCM-based biosensor for the detection of non-small cell lung cancer biomarkers in liquid biopsies., *Talanta.* 260 (2023) 124624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2023.124624>.

- [18] H.J. Lim, T. Saha, B.T. Tey, W.S. Tan, C.W. Ooi, Quartz crystal microbalance-based biosensors as rapid diagnostic devices for infectious diseases., *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 168 (2020) 112513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2020.112513>.
- [19] J.H. Kim, Y.J. Suh, D. Park, H. Yim, H. Kim, H.J. Kim, D.S. Yoon, K.S. Hwang, Technological advances in electrochemical biosensors for the detection of disease biomarkers., *Biomed. Eng. Lett.* 11 (2021) 309–334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13534-021-00204-w>.
- [20] L. Jing, C. Xie, Q. Li, M. Yang, S. Li, H. Li, F. Xia, Electrochemical biosensors for the analysis of breast cancer biomarkers: from design to application., *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 269–296. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.1c04475>.
- [21] J. Wu, H. Liu, W. Chen, B. Ma, H. Ju, Device integration of electrochemical biosensors., *Nat. Rev. Bioeng.* 1 (2023) 346–360. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44222-023-00032-w>.
- [22] A. Joshi, A. Vishnu G K, T. Sakorikar, A.M. Kamal, J.S. Vaidya, H.J. Pandya, Recent advances in biosensing approaches for point-of-care breast cancer diagnostics: challenges and future prospects., *Nanoscale Adv.* 3 (2021) 5542–5564. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1na00453k>.
- [23] N. Wongkaew, M. Simsek, C. Griesche, A.J. Baeumner, Functional Nanomaterials and Nanostructures Enhancing Electrochemical Biosensors and Lab-on-a-Chip Performances: Recent Progress, Applications, and Future Perspective., *Chem. Rev.* 119 (2019) 120–194. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.8b00172>.
- [24] V. Vanova, K. Mitrevska, V. Milosavljevic, D. Hynek, L. Richtera, V. Adam, Peptide-based electrochemical biosensors utilized for protein detection., *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 180 (2021) 113087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2021.113087>.
- [25] X. Wang, Z. Zhang, G. Wu, C. Xu, J. Wu, X. Zhang, J. Liu, Applications of electrochemical biosensors based on functional antibody-modified screen-printed electrodes: a review., *Anal. Methods.* 14 (2021) 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ay01570b>.
- [26] A. Villalonga, A.M. Pérez-Calabuig, R. Villalonga, Electrochemical biosensors based on nucleic acid aptamers., *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 412 (2020) 55–72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-019-02226-x>.
- [27] M. Patel, M. Agrawal, A. Srivastava, Signal amplification strategies in electrochemical biosensors *via* antibody immobilization and nanomaterial-based transducers, *Mater. Adv.* 3 (2022) 8864–8885. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2MA00427E>.
- [28] M. Zamani, V. Yang, L. Maziashvili, G. Fan, C.M. Klapperich, A.L. Furst, Surface Requirements for Optimal Biosensing with Disposable Gold Electrodes., *ACS Meas. Au.* 2 (2022) 91–95. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmeasuresciau.1c00042>.
- [29] M. Zamani, C.M. Klapperich, A.L. Furst, Recent advances in gold electrode fabrication for low-resource setting biosensing., *Lab Chip.* 23 (2023) 1410–1419. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2lc00552b>.
- [30] I. Podunavac, M. Kukkar, V. Léguillier, F. Rizzotto, Z. Pavlovic, L. Janjušević, V. Costache, V. Radonic, J. Vidic, Low-cost goldleaf electrode as a platform for Escherichia coli immunodetection., *Talanta.* 259 (2023) 124557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2023.124557>.
- [31] I. Kundacina, M. Kukkar, I. Nastasijevic, S. Jankovic, R. Mitrovic, V. Radonic, Rapid and Cost-Effective Fabrication of Biosensors for Salmonella Detection, in: *2023 IEEE SENSORS*, IEEE, 2023: pp. 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SENSORS56945.2023.10325027>.

- [32] S. Kittler, M. Besleaga, J. Ebner, O. Spadiut, Protein l—more than just an affinity ligand, *Processes*. 9 (2021) 874. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9050874>.
- [33] T. Romih, I. Konjević, L. Žibret, I. Fazarinc, A. Beltram, D. Majer, M. Finšgar, S.B. Hočevnar, The Effect of Preconditioning Strategies on the Adsorption of Model Proteins onto Screen-Printed Carbon Electrodes., *Sensors*. 22 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22114186>.
- [34] S. Kittler, J. Ebner, M. Besleaga, J. Larsbrink, B. Darnhofer, R. Birner-Gruenberger, S. Schobesberger, C.K. Akhgar, A. Schwaighofer, B. Lendl, O. Spadiut, Recombinant protein L: production, purification and characterization of a universal binding ligand., *J. Biotechnol.* 359 (2022) 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2022.10.002>.
- [35] T. Tran, E. Martinsson, R. Gustavsson, O. Tronarp, M. Nilsson, K.R. Hansson, I. Lundström, C.-F. Mandenius, D. Aili, Process integrated biosensors for real-time monitoring of antibodies for automated affinity purification., *Anal. Methods*. 14 (2022) 4555–4562. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ay01567f>.
- [36] Octet® Protein L (ProL) Biosensors, (n.d.). <https://shop.sartorius.com/at/p/octet-protein-l-prol-biosensors/Bio-Layer-Interferometry-ProL-Biosensors> (accessed January 11, 2024).
- [37] N. Elgrishi, K.J. Rountree, B.D. McCarthy, E.S. Rountree, T.T. Eisenhart, J.L. Dempsey, A practical beginner’s guide to cyclic voltammetry, *J. Chem. Educ.* 95 (2017) 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.7b00361>.
- [38] D.R. Chowdhury, L. Spiccia, S.S. Amritphale, A. Paul, A. Singh, A robust iron oxyhydroxide water oxidation catalyst operating under near neutral and alkaline conditions, *J. Mater. Chem. A*. 4 (2016) 3655–3660. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6TA00313C>.
- [39] A. Ulman, Formation and Structure of Self-Assembled Monolayers., *Chem. Rev.* 96 (1996) 1533–1554. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr9502357>.
- [40] J.C. Love, L.A. Estroff, J.K. Kriebel, R.G. Nuzzo, G.M. Whitesides, Self-assembled monolayers of thiolates on metals as a form of nanotechnology., *Chem. Rev.* 105 (2005) 1103–1169. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr0300789>.
- [41] C.K.A. Nyamekye, S.C. Weibel, E.A. Smith, Directional Raman scattering spectra of metal–sulfur bonds at smooth gold and silver substrates, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 52 (2021) 1246–1255. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.6124>.
- [42] R. Holze, The adsorption of thiophenol on gold—a spectroelectrochemical study., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 17 (2015) 21364–21372. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5cp00884k>.
- [43] C.S. Levin, B.G. Janesko, R. Bardhan, G.E. Scuseria, J.D. Hartgerink, N.J. Halas, Chain-length-dependent vibrational resonances in alkanethiol self-assembled monolayers observed on plasmonic nanoparticle substrates., *Nano Lett.* 6 (2006) 2617–2621. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl062283k>.
- [44] A. Rygula, K. Majzner, K.M. Marzec, A. Kaczor, M. Pilarczyk, M. Baranska, Raman spectroscopy of proteins: a review, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 44 (2013) 1061–1076. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.4335>.
- [45] A.Ch. Lazanas, M.I. Prodromidis, Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy—a tutorial, *ACS Meas. Au.* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmesuresciau.2c00070>.
- [46] P. Parkkila, K. Härkönen, P. Ilvonen, S. Laitinen, T. Viitala, Protein A/G-based surface plasmon resonance biosensor for regenerable antibody-mediated capture and analysis of

- nanoparticles, *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*. 654 (2022) 130015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.130015>.
- [47] D.C. Harris, *Quantitative Chemical Analysis*, 7th ed., W. H. Freeman, 2006.
- [48] S. Wignarajah, I. Chianella, I.E. Tothill, Development of Electrochemical Immunosensors for HER-1 and HER-2 Analysis in Serum for Breast Cancer Patients, *Biosensors*. 13 (2023) 355. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios13030355>.
- [49] W. Wang, R. Han, M. Chen, X. Luo, Antifouling peptide hydrogel based electrochemical biosensors for highly sensitive detection of cancer biomarker HER2 in human serum., *Anal. Chem.* 93 (2021) 7355–7361. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.1c01350>.
- [50] X. Yang, P. Chen, X. Zhang, H. Zhou, Z. Song, W. Yang, X. Luo, An electrochemical biosensor for HER2 detection in complex biological media based on two antifouling materials of designed recognizing peptide and PEG., *Anal. Chim. Acta*. 1252 (2023) 341075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2023.341075>.
- [51] M. Shamsipur, M. Emami, L. Farzin, R. Saber, A sandwich-type electrochemical immunosensor based on in situ silver deposition for determination of serum level of HER2 in breast cancer patients., *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 103 (2018) 54–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2017.12.022>.
- [52] L. Wang, H. Xie, X. Zhou, Y. Lin, Y. Qin, J. Yang, J. Zhao, G. Li, An electrochemical biosensor to identify the phenotype of aggressive breast cancer cells., *Chem. Commun.* 59 (2023) 3890–3893. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3cc00611e>.
- [53] Y. Zhang, N. Li, Y. Xu, X. Liu, Y. Ma, Z. Huang, H. Luo, C. Hou, D. Huo, A novel electrochemical biosensor based on AMNFs@ZIF-67 nano composite material for ultrasensitive detection of HER2., *Bioelectrochemistry*. 150 (2023) 108362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioelechem.2022.108362>.
- [54] D. Li, W. Zhang, M. Miao, Y. Liu, H. Yang, A high-performance PEDOT:PSS platform electrochemical biosensor for the determination of HER2 based on carboxyl-functionalized MWCNTs and ARGET ATRP, *New J. Chem.* 47 (2023) 15579–15587. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3NJ00297G>.